

A Study on Managing Conflict among Women Employees in IT Sector Bangalore

Dr. G.Balamurugan¹ and M.Sreeleka²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Management Studies, Anna University(BIT-Campus), Tiruchirappalli, INDIA

²PG Student, Department of Management Studies, Anna University(BIT-Campus),Tiruchirappalli, INDIA

¹Corresponding Author: drgbalamurugan@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Conflict management is used to resolve the problems between the interpersonal skills in the organization. Now a days the conflict arises due to the non-understanding between each and every one. The communication is also the major thing to get into conflict inside the organization. Conflict is a situation when two or more people face disagreements. The conflict resolution is the process which reach a peace full resolution to a dispute. In this paper we are going to see the conflict resolution for women employees in the IT sector by using the descriptive tool.

Keywords-- Conflict Management, Conflict Resolution, Women Employees

Positive result of conflict and negative result of conflict are here they are

Positive Result of Conflict

- 1) Reconciliation of the interest to the disputing parties
- 2) A sharpened sense of identity and solidarity
- 3) Interaction
- 4) Internal change
- 5) Clarifying the real problem

Conflict often occurs in groups because they are

- 1) Increased trust
- 2) Incensed productivity and results
- 3) Group unity

Negative Result

Often the positive benefits of conflict have been overshadowed by harmful consequence that results when disputing parties attempt to achieve their own goal at the expense of others. Such the forcing exchanges between or often bring about an escalation of the conflict that is difficult to reverse. When forcing methods are used, any of the following negative consequences can follow.

- 1) Minor difference have been escalating into major conflicts that involving actions imposed by a power of person or a group on another, resulting in greater loss to the system as a whole.
- 2) The number of issues in the conflict can be increased, resulting in greater complexity and in greater difficulty for managing the situation.
- 3) Specifies can give way to global concerns, which often cause the person to be equated with and confused with the issues at stake or the entire relationship between the disputing parties to be called into question.
- 4) The intention can shift from getting a specific interest satisfied for beating the other parties to all costs.
- 5) The number of parties can increases of making it even more difficulty to have the de-escalate the conflict.

I. INTRODUCTION

Conflict resolution is one of the most important situations when two or more people come to conflict and the conceptual methods and processes involved in facilitating the peaceful ending of the conflict and retribution. The term conflict resolution has been used interchangeably with dispute resolution can be thought to encompass the use of nonviolent resistance measure by conflicted parties in an attempt to promote effective resolution.

Conflict Resolution

Conflict resolution is the process by which two or more parties by which two or more parties reach a peaceful resolution to a dispute. Conflict may occur between co-workers or between supervisors and subordinates or between services providers and their clients or customers. Conflict can also occur between groups, such as management and the labour force or between whole departments.

Consequences of Conflict

Conflict can be neither can be positive or negative consequences where the parties involved and for the larger social system of which the disputing parties are members.

Conflict outcomes

Conflict Resolution Process

STEP 1: The recognition by the parties which involved in that a problem exists in the organization

STEP 2: Mutual agreement is to address the issue and to find some resolution.

STEP 3: An effort to understand the perspective of the individuals and concerns of the opposing individual or group.

STEP 4: Identifying changes in attitude, behaviour and approaches to work by both sides that will lessen negative feeling.

STEP 5: Recognizing triggers to episodes of conflict.

STEP 6: Interventions by third parties such as human resource representatives or higher-level managers to mediate.

STEP 7: A willingness by one or both parties to compromise each other.

STEP 8: Agreement on a plan to address difference.

STEP 9: Monitoring the impact of agreements for change.

STEP 10: Disciplining or terminating employees who resist efforts to defuse conflicts.

Types of Conflict Resolution Skills

Assertiveness

A supervisors might take the initiatives to convene a meeting between two employees who have engaged in a public dispute. An employee might be seeking out a person with whom they are having conflict to suggest working together and to find out the ways to co-exist more peacefully.

Articulate, Balanced approach, Decisive, Delegation, Leadership, Management, Problem solving, Self control.

Interviewing and Active Listening

A human resources representative might have to ask questions and listen carefully to determine the nature of a conflict between a supervisor and a subordinate.

Negotiation, Attentiveness, Encouraging, Sense of humor

Empathy

A mediator might encourage empathy by asking employees in conflict to each describe how the other might be feeling and thinking and how the situation might look to the other party.

Empathy is also an important skill for mediators, who must be able to understand each party's perspective without necessarily agreeing with either.

- Asking for feedback
- Building trust
- Compassion
- Trustworthy

Facilitation

Managers of rival departments might facilitate a joint brainstorming session with their teams to generate solutions to ongoing points of conflict. Group facilitation techniques can also be used to avoid triggering conflict during group decision-making, in the first place.

- Collaboration
- Conflict management

- Humble
- Planning
- Teamwork

Mediation Skills

A supervisor might guide subordinates who are in conflict through a process to identify mutually agreeable changes in behaviour.

- Emotional intelligence
- Problem solving
- Decision making
- Measured
- Honesty

Creative problem Solving

A supervisor may redefine the roles of two conflict-prone staff to simply eliminate points of friction. Creatively can also mean finding new win/win solutions.

- Brainstorming solution
- Collaborating
- Goal integration

Accountability

A supervisor might document conflict-initiating behaviours exhibited by a chronic complainer as preparation for a performance appraisal. In this way the supervisor helps establish accountability since the employee can no longer pretend the problem is not happening.

- Adaptable
- Dynamic
- Flexible
- Versatile

More Conflict Resolution Skills

- Calmness
- Let it go
- Logical
- Avoid punishing

II. CONFLICT RESOLUTION MODEL

Step 1: Awareness

This is the stage where it involves an awareness of the negative emotional states in a conflict. It emerges around the awareness of perceived difference, usually because of:

- An assertion where one party attempts to influence another party of parties to achieve his or her needs.
- One party takes a stand on an issue that is opposed by another party or parties.
- One party attempts to exercise power or control over the actions of behaviour of the other party or parties.
- Imposed sanction, where one party intentionally harms the other to get their needs met.

Step 2: Self Preparation

This second stage of the conflict resolution model involves accessing a resourceful state, deciding your outcome and planning the step to achieve it. This stage can take place quickly or involves a considerable amount of time depending on the context.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is based on the analytic in nature. The primary data were collected through the structured questionnaire. This study is based on the conflict that arises in between the women employees in the IT sector. The respondents is recorded on 5 point Likert scale with SA, A, N, D, SD.

Where SA-Strongly Agree, A-Agree, N-Neutral, D-Disagree, SD-Strongly Disagree

IV. DISCRIPTION OF THE TOOL USED

The questionnaire had 30 items they are demographic variables are collected in detail no of respondents namely age group, number of children, conflict arise because of the family and professional.

V. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The data are analysed by using the statistical tool. I have used simple percentage analysis and coefficient correlation test. Which is used to see the significant relationship between the dependent variables and independent variables.

Age	Respondents	Percentage
Below 30	8	40
30-40	5	25
40-50	7	35

Above 50	0	0
Total	20	100

Marital status	Respondents	Percentage
Single	10	50
Married	10	50
Total	20	100

Education Qualification	Respondents	Percentage
10 th	0	0
12 th	9	45
UG degree	8	40
PG degree	3	15
Total	20	100

I will control my self when there is conflict
20 responses

• yes
• no

VI. COEFFICIENT CORRELATION

1) Correlation between Age and I learn to forgive others

H0: There is no relationship between age and I learn to forgive others

H1: There is relationship between age and I learn to forgive others

Correlations

		AGE	I learn to forgive
AGE	Pearson Correlation	1	.621**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.003
	N	20	20
I learn to forgive	Pearson Correlation	.621**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	
	N	20	20

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Thus the result concluded that is H1 is accepted. Hence there is a relationship between the Age and I learn to forgive others

2) Correlation between marital status and I tried to understand his/her point of view

H0: There is no relationship between age and I tried to understand his/her point of view

H1: There is relationship between age and I tried to understand his/her point of view

Correlations

		Marital status	I tried to understand
Marital status	Pearson Correlation	1	.a
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N		

		Sig. (2-tailed)	
I tried to understand	Pearson Correlation	.a	.a
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	20	20

a. Cannot be computed because at least one of the variables is constant.

Thus the result concluded that is H1 is accepted. Hence there is a relationship between the Marital status and I tried to understand his/her point of view

3) Correlation between Age and I try to compromise conflict between each other

H0: There is no relationship between age and I try to compromise conflict between each other.

H1: There is no relationship between age and I try to compromise conflict between each other.

Correlations

		AGE	I try to compromise
AGE	Pearson Correlation	1	-.344
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.137
	N	20	20
I try to compromise	Pearson Correlation	-.344	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.137	
	N	20	20

Thus the result concluded that is H0 is accepted. Hence there is no relationship between the Age and I try to compromise conflict between each other.

4) Correlation between Age and I will control myself when there is a conflict

H0: There is no relationship between age and I will control myself when there is a conflict

H1: There is no relationship between age and I will control myself when there is a conflict

Correlations

		AGE	I will control myself when there is conflict
AGE	Pearson Correlation	1	-.451*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.046
	N	20	20
I will control myself when there is conflict	Pearson Correlation	-.451*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.046	
	N	20	20

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Thus the result concluded that is H0 is accepted. Hence there is no relationship between the Age and I will try to control myself when there is a conflict.

- 5) Correlation between marital status and I avoid problems in some situation.

H0: There is no relationship between age and I avoid problems in some situation.

H1: There is no relationship between age and I avoid problems in some situation.

Correlations

		Marital status	I avoid problems in some situation
Marital status	Pearson Correlation	1	.626**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.003
	N	20	20
I avoid problems in some situation	Pearson Correlation	.626**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	
	N	20	20

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Thus the result concluded that is H1 is accepted. Hence there is relationship between the Marital status and I will try to control myself when there is a conflict.

VII. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- 1) The Majority (45%) of the respondents are from the Age of Below 30.
- 2) The Majority (50%) of the respondents are unmarried.
- 3) The Majority (45%) of the respondents are educated in PG degree.
- 4) The Majority (100%) of the respondents are agree that they can control them self in conflict.

Correlation Result

- 1) There is a positive relationship among Age and I learn to forgive others
- 2) There is a positive relationship among marital status and I tried to understand his/her point of view.
- 3) There is a negative relationship between Age and I try to compromise conflict between each other's.
- 4) There is a negative relationship between Age and I will try to control myself when there is a conflict.
- 5) There is a positive relationship between Marital status and I will try to control myself when there is a conflict.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The work life balance of women employees plays a major role in IT sector. Where the conflict arises mostly with them and more difficulties in managing their own life and in professional life. Thus, the women employee should manage the conflict among them it depends on the demographic variables. In this paper it shows that all women are managing their conflict and how the relationship between the variables whether it is positive or negative. So that this paper says the conflict resolution and by using the models and process the resolution can be solved and the conflict can be managed.

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